

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s44264-025-00118-5>

Narrowing farmland biodiversity knowledge gaps with Digital Agriculture

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Digital Agriculture – broadly defined as the use of digital technologies and data to manage and optimize agricultural production systems – holds significant but largely untapped potential for biodiversity monitoring. Both fields share many (semi-)automated data collection technologies, analytical methods and workflows, but remain largely disconnected – and are sometimes even perceived as incompatible – in research, education and practice. Here, we explore how existing data streams from Digital Agriculture can directly contribute with primary biodiversity data required by policy-relevant applications, linking them to the Essential Biodiversity Variables framework. We discuss the benefits of this integration, its challenges, and outline pathways for its adoption with respect to ongoing advances in biodiversity science and policy. This integration could improve the precision of biodiversity conservation in farmland, and accelerate transitions to sustainable agriculture – an urgent priority to safeguard nature and its contribution to people.

Both agriculture and biodiversity science are undergoing rapid digital transformations. Research fields that were once constrained by sparse, irregular, or coarse-resolution data are now becoming increasingly data-rich. In agriculture, the widespread adoption of automated sensors and digital technologies for precision farming (hereafter ‘Digital Agriculture’) – including cameras¹, drones², and genetic sampling^{3,4} enables continuous, high-resolution monitoring^{5,6}. For instance, drones now support a wide range of tasks, such as sowing of seeds, spreading fertilizers and feeds, counting livestock, and the monitoring of crop health and yield⁷. These data are used to maximize yields, reduce food waste, minimize inputs, and increase the resilience and sustainability of farming systems⁸. Biodiversity monitoring is being revolutionized by the same sensing technologies^{9–11}, which use virtually the same types of data, and similar sensor networks, for unprecedented species- and community-level biodiversity assessments^{12,13}. This convergence in technologies creates a unique opportunity: to align agricultural and ecological monitoring infrastructures, methods, and objectives. Through digital agriculture, sensors established for digital field and farm management could also generate primary biodiversity data required for biodiversity monitoring and policy-relevant reporting^{14,15}. In

fact, both applications may even employ the same analytical methods (e.g., same image segmentation algorithms^{16,17}), increasing the potential for interoperability. Notably, some primary biodiversity data are already generated through Digital Agriculture (Fig. 1), though collected for purposes other than biodiversity monitoring (e.g., pest control^{11,18,19}, soil management^{20–22}, crop phenotyping^{23–25}). In some cases, primary biodiversity data may even be collected unintentionally and treated as ‘noise’ (e.g., molehills in drone imagery²⁶).

A growing body of literature recognizes the potential of Digital Agriculture for biodiversity. For instance, farm management data and information systems have been proposed as conservation tools by identifying low-productivity zones suitable for conservation strips⁶. At the policy-science interface, there is a growing push for the widespread adoption of Digital Agriculture. The 2022–2031 strategic plan of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), for example, promotes the integration of digital technologies to optimize the use of natural resources, reduce environmental impacts, and encourage biodiversity-friendly farming methods²⁷. This aligns with the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) targets, particularly those related to sustainable land management (Target 10), reduced

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Fig. 1 | Uncovering biodiversity through Digital Agriculture. Biodiversity monitoring (a) is supported by various technologies, including drones (b), camera traps (c), eDNA obtained from genetic samples (d), and passive acoustic monitoring (e). These technologies record species occurrences and partly abundances, enabling subsequent assessments of species distributions and community compositions (in blue; f). Digital Agriculture (g) uses the same technologies in routine field and farm management (shown in red). Drones and camera traps (h), sometimes combined with passive acoustic monitoring (i), monitor pest occurrences and damages.

Simultaneously, weeding robots facilitate the detection and removal of weeds (j) that compete with crops for space and nutrients. Soil sampling (k), often used to control for nutrient availability, may also support the extraction of eDNA to control for harmful pathogens (l). Because biodiversity monitoring (a) shares technology requirements with Digital Agriculture (g), data from the latter, if made accessible to biodiversity monitoring experts, could improve assessments of species populations and community composition (in blue; f).

food waste (Target 16), and lower agricultural pollution (Target 7). However, despite these overlapping objectives, biodiversity monitoring initiatives largely operate independently of the rapidly evolving Digital Agriculture sector. This disconnect limits the integration of high-resolution, near real-time agricultural and biodiversity data, potentially missing valuable opportunities for more precise and adaptive conservation actions.

Indeed, such data integration remains rare among state-of-the-art agroecological monitoring initiatives. While meta-analyses have attempted to link yield and biodiversity measured at the same locations^{28,29}, many biodiversity studies still rely on (sub)national agricultural statistics to assess biodiversity-yield interactions^{30,31}. This reliance often stems from a lack of direct and spatially representative measurements of crop production in areas where biodiversity is surveyed, for instance, due to land access restrictions³². When aggregated statistics are used, assessments of biodiversity change inherit temporal inconsistencies and quality issues³³, which may additionally lack ecologically meaningful thematic and spatial detail³⁴. Because biodiversity data frequently originate from short-term or taxonomically narrow monitoring efforts^{35–37}, aligning biodiversity and crop production data becomes increasingly challenging. Data misalignments and biases can influence the conclusions of biodiversity change assessments³⁸, resulting in biased perceptions of biodiversity responses to agricultural management practices.

Ensuring the robustness of biodiversity change assessments is critical. Policy frameworks for protecting and restoring nature (e.g., GBF, EU Nature Restoration Regulation) rely on these measurements—and on the inference of change drivers—to assess progress towards biodiversity targets³⁹. In agroecosystems, monitoring species occurrences, abundances, and traits is especially important, as their combination informs on variations in the provision and stability of nature’s contributions to people (e.g., pollination, pest control), which in turn influence human well-being and food security⁴⁰. To effectively capture functional changes in agroecosystems, biodiversity monitoring must be

systematic and accompanied by field- and farm-level management data. Such integration allows improved understanding of temporal variations in biodiversity responses to the sowing, growth, and harvest cycles of crops^{41,42}, and to the sensitivity of those responses to local environmental and socio-economic context³⁵.

In this paper, we discuss how Digital Agriculture can meet these requirements, enabling more systematic and concurrent measurements on biodiversity and agricultural production. First, based on existing literature, we demonstrate that biodiversity monitoring can, in principle, already be enabled by common applications in Digital Agriculture. Second, we map core data streams to specific, policy-relevant indicators on the status and change of biodiversity. Third, we propose pathways to improve the operationalization of Digital Agriculture for monitoring biodiversity. Finally, we reflect on ongoing investments in the digitalization of agroecosystems, and discuss the key challenges, limitations and implications of this approach.

Opportunities for monitoring biodiversity through Digital Agriculture

Digital Agriculture technologies are primarily designed to monitor variables within cultivated lands, particularly croplands. Therefore, their value for biodiversity monitoring is limited to the collection of data on taxa occurring within those lands. However, despite the fact that semi-natural habitats are key for sustaining farmland biodiversity⁴³, production fields can host large portions of known species pools (e.g., up to 51% of farmland vascular plants, earthworms, spiders, and wild bees in Europe⁴⁴). These species are commonly affected by—and adapted to—agriculture-related habitat transformations^{45,46}, driving temporal and spatial variations in biodiversity patterns^{41,42}. Data on the cropland-dwelling fraction of biodiversity may already be generated through Digital Agriculture (Fig. 1). Here, we exemplify this potential through three, common applications of Digital Agriculture generating relevant, yet underused, data on species occurrences and

traits: the control of pests, diseases, and weeds (2.1), the monitoring of soil nutrients and pathogens (2.2), and the phenotyping of domesticated plants (2.3).

Management of pests, diseases, and weeds

Globally, pests and crop diseases cause an estimated 20–40% loss in food production each year, amounting to approximately US\$220 billion in damages⁴⁷. The most damaging pests include invasive mammals, insects, and birds^{48,49}. Weeds further contribute to crop losses⁵⁰ by competing with crops for water, nutrients and space as well as providing habitat for insect pests, and potentially harboring harmful pathogens⁵¹.

The monitoring and management of pests, diseases, and weeds is a key application of Digital Agriculture, guiding the use of pesticides¹⁹, weed removal⁵², and deterrents (e.g., audio playbacks of animal calls to repel competing species⁵³). Drones equipped with RGB, multi- or hyperspectral sensors, or stationary cameras help detect crop damages caused by insects⁵⁴, rodents⁵⁵ or larger mammals⁵⁶. Alternatively, traps and acoustic sensors can be used to locate pests (e.g., insects⁵⁷, birds¹⁸) and can potentially inform on their seasonal occurrence and abundance (i.e., phenology)⁵⁸. Drones, sometimes combining RGB and lidar sensors, may also be used for detecting weeds⁵⁹ and plant disease².

Biodiversity surveys often rely on the same data and technologies. Drones have long been used for this purpose¹¹, enhancing estimates of species richness and abundances (e.g., for birds⁶⁰ or endangered and elusive mammals⁶¹). Similarly, camera traps are commonly used to detect various taxa^{9,62}—although rarely in agricultural lands⁶³—as are camera-equipped insect traps⁶⁴ and passive acoustic sensors⁶⁵. The generated imagery and audio recordings may then be analyzed with AI-based models to identify and distinguish species^{66–69}.

Monitoring of soil nutrients and pathogens

Poor soil conditions are a critical constraint on food production globally. The United Nations estimate that up to 40% of the world's land is degraded, affecting close to 3.2 billion people⁷⁰. Soil salinity alone, which hinders crop productivity⁷¹, has led to reductions in agricultural yields of up to 70% in the affected areas⁷². The global costs of land degradation are substantial, estimated at US\$ 878 billion per year, with regard to agricultural productivity, nature's contributions to people, and other related sectors⁷⁰.

Periodic assessments of soil health are essential for optimizing crop productivity, and thus a key application of Digital Agriculture. Soil sampling at the field-level shows variations in mineral compositions⁷³, nutrient contents^{74,75}, and functionality²⁰. In this process, the abundance of specific microorganisms may be monitored as a proxy for soil quality (e.g., earthworms⁷⁶). More recently, thanks to advanced genetic testing, the use of environmental DNA (eDNA) has become increasingly affordable and efficient²², enabling detections of root-level microbial communities affecting plant growth^{3,22,74}. Data collected on the field can then be combined with imagery from drones or satellites to map soil quality indicator⁷⁷. This can guide site-specific recommendations for use of fertilizers²¹ and pesticides⁷⁸, and of crop rotation schedules⁷⁹.

The monitoring of soil biodiversity relies on similar inputs. eDNA, in particular, has been shown effective in measuring soil biodiversity¹⁰, and may also inform on occurrences on unobserved—and potentially elusive—species that transverse sampled locations⁸⁰. The use of eDNA for biodiversity monitoring may, in the future, also integrate drone and satellite imagery to map the diversity of soil-dwelling bacteria and fungi beyond sampled locations⁸¹.

Phenotyping of domesticated species

Over the past three decades, approximately \$3.8 trillion in crop and livestock production has been lost due to disasters⁸². These events have contributed to increased food prices, a trend expected to continue under climate change⁸³. This has major implications for food security, putting millions of people at risk of malnutrition.

Phenotyping, which implies measuring and analyzing structural, physiological, and biochemical characteristics (i.e., traits) of plants and animals, can help tackle these issues. Digital agriculture systems may use phenotyping as part of routine management of crops throughout their lifecycle, optimizing the spatial and temporal allocation of natural and chemical resources (e.g., through targeted irrigation⁸⁴). This can be enabled through the use of multi- and hyperspectral or lidar imagery, derived from drones or satellites, to track potential growth deficiencies revealed by, for instance, low carbon concentrations⁸⁵ or spatial variations in the vertical structure of plant stands⁸⁶. Drone imagery may also be used to monitor livestock health, such as by informing on the body mass, temperature, or feed intake of individual animals⁸⁷.

Trait-based approaches are increasingly used in biodiversity monitoring. This enables data to inform on the response of organisms to environmental change, species adaptation patterns, and overall population or ecosystem health. In this process, imagery from drones is mostly used to record functional traits of plant communities⁸⁸, including wild plants occurring in agricultural fields¹⁶. More recently, as in livestock management applications, drones have been used to infer traits of wild mammals, such as body mass⁸⁹.

Digital Agriculture As Vehicle For Sustainable Transitions

Biodiversity monitoring through Digital Agriculture would ideally support a technological-ecological transition from output-optimizing (focused on crop growth and health) to ecosystem condition-optimizing. It would thus allow a transition from reactive to proactive biodiversity management as real-time and spatially explicit data would enable continuous monitoring of species and ecosystem health, making biodiversity protection an integral, ongoing part of field and farm management (Fig. 2).

Through Digital Agriculture, cultivated lands, which now comprise nearly half of the world's habitable land⁹⁰, may become “living labs” where key biodiversity data are regularly collected. Time-series on species distributions and abundances, combined with those on crop growth and agronomic management, may be used to infer dynamics in ecological responses to environmental change⁹¹ potentially overlooked by structured, yet seasonal and temporally limited, biodiversity surveys. This would facilitate new insights into ecological dynamics related to movement phenology⁴² and habitat use in agricultural land for foraging⁴⁶, predation⁹², or reproduction⁹³. If data from multiple farms is integrated through state-of-the-art sampling designs⁹⁴, Digital Agriculture could help sustain scalable causal inference frameworks essential for policy-relevant biodiversity change reporting⁹⁵ and evidence-based agricultural management^{96,97}.

To enable insights relevant to both policy-making and reporting, Digital Agriculture data can be aligned with the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) framework by the Group on Earth Observation Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON)⁹⁸. Long endorsed by the biodiversity research community^{98–100}, EBVs were proposed as a means of standardizing and streamlining biodiversity monitoring and reporting across scales⁹⁸, and now form the basis for headline indicator 21.1 of the GBF¹⁰¹. Many EBVs require species-focused reference data for their calculation and calibration, and much of these data can be derived by digital technologies used in both biodiversity monitoring and Digital Agriculture^{102,103}—as described in section 2.

Digital Agriculture therefore can enable these data streams, thereby supporting direct (or indirect) calculations of several EBVs (Fig. 3, Supplementary Table 1). For example, species observations derived through the monitoring of pests, weeds, diseases, and soil health can be used directly to calculate EBVs on species abundances. Similarly, phenotyping data can inform EBVs on species-level traits, for example morphological (e.g., plant height, body size of insects) physiological (e.g., nutrient content, body temperature), and production-related traits (e.g. number of flowers or nests). Time series of these EBVs, enabled through the regular, systematic monitoring of crop growth and of associated biodiversity, could further support assessment of EBVs on the phenology of single species, and

Fig. 2 | Potential for farm- and field-level causal inference. **a** In a biodiversity-focused survey, species observations (bird icon, in blue) are detected with passive acoustic monitoring. The timing of the survey is aligned with the main breeding season of the target species (blue outline). Species detections are paired with categorical information on crop type (in dark green), common practice in state-of-the-art agroecological research. **b** Passive acoustic sensors are used to detect crop-

damaging birds, while drones help monitor crop growth, damages, and health, but could also enable time-series on species-level bird abundances (c) based on detections recorded outside the breeding season (bird icons, in black). **d** With time-series on agriculture and biodiversity, together with their uncertainties (shaded ribbons), we can formally measure the presence and magnitude of causal effects, such as relating to biodiversity-yield or predator-prey interactions.

community-level variations of trait, taxonomic, phylogenetic, and interaction diversity. If monitoring capabilities are integrated at landscape level, EBVs on species movements and distributions may be inferred (e.g., using networks of cameras⁹, acoustic sensors¹⁰⁴). Concurrent data on the growth of crops could further inform EBVs on ecosystem function and structure. Specifically, phenotyping data and management could enable EBVs on the vertical profile, live cover fraction, and primary productivity of agroecosystems, and on their disturbance regimes (e.g., relating to sowing, in-season management and harvesting).

Challenges And Enablers Of Biodiversity Monitoring Through Digital Agriculture

National biodiversity monitoring schemes are required to guide conservation action¹⁰⁵. Yet, such programs remain absent in most countries, or largely underdeveloped or underfunded¹⁰⁵. This may be explained by the costs of such programs, reaching millions of US\$ per year^{106,107}. While such investments are feasible for most countries of the Global North^{106,107}, in the Global South, global disparities in economic capacity and institutional stability persist¹⁰⁸. Investments in Digital Agriculture could help balance the organizational and financial burdens of biodiversity monitoring in agroecosystems, enabling the monitoring of emergent conservation issues (e.g., human-wildlife conflicts due to cropland expansion⁹²).

Indeed, investments in Digital Agriculture are accelerating. As of January 2025, the FAO recorded 449 ongoing, public or private initiatives aimed at advancing the use of Digital Agriculture across all continents¹⁰⁹, ~89% of which are applied to managing farms of all sizes (Fig. 4a). While ~90% of all initiatives concentrate in Europe and Asia (Fig. 4b), every country hosts at least some initiatives that apply Digital Agriculture using automated sensors, Big Data and Artificial Intelligence¹⁰⁹. In the Global South, most private investments in the agricultural sector are already directed at digital innovation¹¹⁰, notably in countries such as Thailand and Vietnam, where the density of drones per km² of cropland ranks amongst the highest⁷. These current and future investments in Digital Agriculture hold great potential to enhance national biodiversity monitoring capabilities, provided that digitalization efforts *i*) tackle inequities in digitalization capacity, *ii*) provide direct benefits for farmers, *iii*) enable data

sharing and protect data privacy, and *iv*) directly account for data gaps, biases, and quality issues. In this section, we discuss these aspects and pathways to enable them.

Equitable and inclusive digitalization to mitigate socio-economic risks

While investments in Digital Agriculture are increasing globally, digitalization rates still vary greatly across farming systems. The development of new technologies tends to favor large, capital-intensive farms, which can then quickly adopt new technologies¹¹¹, while smallholder and family farms, despite largely welcoming digitalization¹¹²⁻¹¹⁴, often lack the required technical support¹¹² and policy incentives¹¹⁵. Recent data on the global diffusion of agricultural drone technologies indicate that, beyond income levels, factors, such as labor scarcity, the age structure of the farming population, subsidies, and regulatory frameworks also play key roles⁷.

For instance, in South Africa, smallholder farmers struggle with high labor and maintenance costs and weak public infrastructure¹¹⁶. In Ghana, digitalization improved farmer organization into groups, but resources remain insufficient to enhance overall working condition¹¹⁷. Without adequate political and expert support, smaller farms may struggle to compete economically, exacerbating existing socioeconomic inequalities. In addition, if digitalization efforts do not succeed in smallholder- and family-owned lands, which compose over 90% of the world's farms¹¹⁸, Digital Agriculture may exacerbate the spatial, temporal, and taxonomic biases affecting global biodiversity data¹¹⁹.

Ongoing development programs can help guide future digitalization efforts. For instance, in the Global North, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) reserved €8 billion between 2021 and 2027 to foster the digital transformation of rural communities, with particular focus on family farms¹²⁰. In the Global South, national incentive schemes are gradually emerging^{121,122}. These are supported by international development programs (e.g., UN-led 50 by 2030 program¹²³), some aiming at developing monitoring capabilities in rural areas (e.g., FAO's AGRI-NBSAP¹²⁴). However, the effectiveness of such programs rests on the existence of inclusive policies and region-sensitive governance^{7,125,126}. Digitalization efforts must consider the socio-economic and environmental contexts of

Fig. 3 | Potential synergies between Digital Agriculture and EBVs. On the left, the different applications of Digital Agriculture highlighted in this paper, namely pest, disease and weed control, soil monitoring, and phenotyping. On the right, Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) per thematic group. Lines link each Digital

Agriculture application with one or multiple EBVs. A detailed description on each EBV, their relevance for agriculture, and their enabling Digital Agriculture Technologies is given in Supplementary Table 1. The data used in this figure is provided as Supplementary Data 1.

a) Digital Agriculture initiatives per farm size

Fig. 4 | Global distribution of initiatives advancing Digital Agriculture. **a** For each continent, the number of ongoing Digital Agriculture initiatives recorded by the FAO¹⁰⁹ that target farm-level management. Colors distinguish initiatives based on the farm size they target, with sizes classified according to FAO’s Agritech Observatory¹⁰⁹: “Small” - typical characteristics associated with “smallholder” farms, such as limited access to resources, finance, and technology; “Medium” - highly

b) Initiatives targeting digital farm management per country

active, specialized farms and agricultural holdings; “Large” - industrial farming. **b** For each country, the proportion of all ongoing Digital Agriculture initiatives targeting farm-level management. This includes sensing technologies, and digital platforms for engaging with field- and farm-level data in decision making. See Supplementary Data 2 to access the plotted data.

rural communities^{127,128}. Context-aware digitalization initiatives ease the adoption of new technologies by resource-constrained smallholder farms¹²⁹, and create new employment opportunities⁷.

Achieving shared benefits through digitalization

Humans remain central to transition towards sustainable agriculture^{130,131}, with farmers ultimately responsible for deciding on uptake of digital technologies, for implementing agri-environmental measures¹²⁶, and for giving access to farmlands for biodiversity data collection. To address this issue, a range of participatory strategies have been proposed¹³², some connecting networks of stakeholders (including farmers), data, tools, and biodiversity monitoring programs¹⁰⁵ (Fig. 5a–e). Modern participatory

approaches aim to incorporate not only ecological objectives, but also cultural, economic, and societal considerations¹⁰⁵ (Fig. 5a, b). Yet, current participatory strategies can impose a considerable burden on farmers. While these strategies may involve farmers in the collection, analysis and reporting of data-driven insights (Fig. 5c–e), this often constitutes a challenging, and time-consuming task, adding to the challenges of farming itself. Simultaneously, despite the vast literature on the biodiversity benefits of agroecological measures, the direct benefits for individual farmers remain uncertain, and scale- and context-dependent³⁵. As a result, generic policy recommendations or incentive schemes may fall short, and may inadvertently fuel negative human perspectives on biodiversity conservation¹³³.

Fig. 5 | Farmer participation strategy. In current participatory strategies, expert communities conduct research on interactions between biodiversity and field management practices (a), and may involve farmers in monitoring activities and data analyses (b). Resulting literature fuels science-based reporting (c). Policymakers use these reports as a basis for legislation (d) aimed at regulating and funding field-level, biodiversity-supporting management practices (e). In this process, farmers

profit from biodiversity monitoring only indirectly. Yet, they are exposed to the uncertainties of biodiversity gains, and of their influence on food production. Biodiversity monitoring, if established through Digital Agriculture, could directly provide insights on agroecosystem conditions and trends (f). Resulting Digital Agriculture data streams would then offer insights on trade-offs between food production and biodiversity (g).

Digital Agriculture may help streamline the involvement of farmers in biodiversity monitoring, as it offers direct, actionable insights about field- and farm-level environmental conditions, enhancing everyday agricultural management (Fig. 5g). In this process, targeted, long-term biodiversity gains could be achieved through state-dependent adjustments of farm management practices to biodiversity observations, potentially also supported through agri-environmental schemes¹³⁴. To enable biodiversity monitoring through farm-level digitalization, projects advancing biodiversity monitoring capabilities (GBF Target 21) could sustain cooperation projects designing, or optimizing, farm-level sensor networks. Indeed, such developments would align with the GBF, which calls for capacity-building, technology transfer, and cooperation in biodiversity monitoring (Target 20). Finally, economic benefits of Digital Agriculture may sustain biodiversity monitoring capabilities beyond a project’s lifespan.

Data ownership and privacy concerns

Digital Agriculture will generate vast quantities of environmental and field-to-farm-level management data, with important questions arising on who owns, controls, and benefits from these data. Over 70% of open data on agriculture originates from satellite-based remote sensing applications¹³⁵.

On the contrary, farm-level data remain largely unavailable and lacking in interoperability¹¹².

Ongoing initiatives are addressing data access limitations. Global programs (e.g., UN-funded CGIAR¹³⁶), nationally-funded expert groups (e.g., FAIRagro in Germany¹³⁷), and multi-national data harmonization projects^{138,139} are rapidly aiming to make farm-level data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). As these initiatives advance, Digital Agriculture data streams can become accessible for biodiversity monitoring. This will require clear and transparent data-sharing agreements to protect data property and rights (GBF targets 21, 22) and to avoid potential misuse of information or surveillance-like dynamics¹⁴⁰. This is critical, given that economic details are involved, such as subsidies linked to participation in agri-environmental schemes. Volunteer and federated data access, as adopted by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), would help preserve data ownership and privacy. Alternatively, data sharing formats may directly reflect national regulations and privacy agreements through custom spatial aggregations¹⁴¹.

However, it is critical that data provision is assured to support reporting requirements. If data are treated exclusively as private property, they may become a commodity reserved for activities with higher financial benefits compared to biodiversity monitoring⁷. In farmland, this may occur

with respect to companies producing and renting machinery, who might impose restrictions over the access of data generated by tractors and other sensors. In Europe, the EU Data Act is setting an important example in tackling this issue, empowering farmers to access and share data from connected farm equipment¹⁴². This gives the managers of farmland control over their operational data, giving users rights to access this data, while also creating obligations for businesses that provide these products.

Integrating ecological knowledge to address data biases

Georeferenced information on the occurrence and abundance of species derived through Digital Agriculture cannot replace structured, long-term data streams required for biodiversity trend reporting. However, it may complement them, helping mitigate pervasive spatial and temporal data gaps and biases in cultivated lands³². For instance, FAIR principles for sharing whole-genome sequencing data obtained from soils¹⁴³ could inform on soil-dwelling species, tackling taxonomic biases in global biodiversity databases¹⁴⁴. Digital Agriculture may also reveal small-bodied species undetected during biodiversity surveys, or when land-access restrictions are in place (e.g., nests of ground-breeding birds¹⁴⁵).

However, Digital Agriculture alone cannot resolve existing data biases. In addition to the taxonomic and body-size-related biases discussed above, its benefits may vary per planted field and be conditioned by crop types and associated management practices. For instance, seasonal and diurnal variations in species distributions may be misaligned with crop growth periods. Biodiversity observations resulting from Digital Agriculture may further be limited in scope, such as targeting the most harmful pest species. Because such biases are very familiar to biodiversity surveyors³⁶, their involvement (e.g., guidance on sensor selection and data collection periods) may enhance the usability of biodiversity data obtained through Digital Agriculture for downstream analyses. This may require improvements in the governance of on-going monitoring schemes and a better involvement of stakeholders¹⁴⁶.

Conclusions

Biodiversity conservation efforts are gaining momentum through international policy, such as the GBF or the EU Nature Restoration Regulation. Many targets outlined in the GBF depend on sustainable farm management¹⁴⁷, which in turn requires concerted monitoring efforts to track biodiversity trends. Digital Agriculture offers a promising, cost-effective pathway to bridge agricultural and biodiversity monitoring. In fact, it employs some of the same technologies and methods used to monitor biodiversity, making derived data—which already captures species occurrences and traits—usable for concurrent biodiversity monitoring, scientific discovery, and learning. Most importantly, this would be achieved without placing additional burdens on farmers, with direct benefits for them. Yet, the monitoring of agriculture and biodiversity remain disconnected in research, practice and education. Explicit integration is needed to minimize monitoring costs and pave the road towards more sustainable future farming systems.

Data availability

No data were collected for this study.

Received: 23 June 2025; Accepted: 5 December 2025;

Published online: 31 January 2026

References

1. Preti, M., Verheggen, F. & Angeli, S. Insect pest monitoring with camera-equipped traps: strengths and limitations. *J. Pest. Sci.* **94**, 203–217 (2021).
2. Zhang, S., Wang, X., Lin, H., Dong, Y. & Qiang, Z. A review of the application of UAV multispectral remote sensing technology in precision agriculture. *Smart Agric. Technol.* **12**, 101406 (2025).
3. Kestel, J. H. et al. Applications of environmental DNA (eDNA) in agricultural systems: current uses, limitations and future prospects. *Sci. Total Environ.* **847**, 157556 (2022).
4. Fang, J., Zhu, X., Wang, C. & Shangguan, L. Applications of DNA technologies in agriculture. *Curr. Genomics* **17**, 379–386 (2016).
5. McFadden, J. *The Digitalisation of Agriculture: A Literature Review and Emerging Policy Issues*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/285cc27d-en>. (2022).
6. Basso, B. & Antle, J. Digital agriculture to design sustainable agricultural systems. *Nat. Sustain.* **3**, 254–256 (2020).
7. Belton, B. et al. Can the global drone revolution make agriculture more sustainable? *Science* **389**, 972–976 (2025).
8. Gebbers, R. & Adamchuk, V. I. Precision agriculture and food security. *Science* **327**, 828–831 (2010).
9. Bruce, T. et al. Large-scale and long-term wildlife research and monitoring using camera traps: a continental synthesis. *Biol. Rev.* **100**, 530–555 (2025).
10. Xing, K. et al. Soil eDNA biomonitoring reveals changes in multitrophic biodiversity and ecological health of agroecosystems. *Environ. Res.* **262**, 119931 (2024).
11. Corcoran, E., Winsen, M., Sudholz, A. & Hamilton, G. Automated detection of wildlife using drones: synthesis, opportunities and constraints. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **12**, 1103–1114 (2021).
12. Hartig, F. et al. Novel community data in ecology—properties and prospects. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* **39**, 280–293 (2024).
13. Besson, M. et al. Towards the fully automated monitoring of ecological communities. *Ecol. Lett.* **25**, 2753–2775 (2022).
14. Danielsen, F. et al. Involving citizens in monitoring the Kunming–Montreal global biodiversity framework. *Nat. Sustain.* **7**, 1730–1739 (2024).
15. Stevenson, S. L. et al. Corroboration and contradictions in global biodiversity indicators. *Biol. Conserv.* **290**, 110451 (2024).
16. Barrasso, C., Krüger, R., Eltner, A. & Cord, A. F. Mapping indicator species of segetal flora for result-based payments in arable land using UAV imagery and deep learning. *Ecol. Indic.* **169**, 112780 (2024).
17. C, S. G. et al. Field-based multispecies weed and crop detection using ground robots and advanced YOLO models: a data and model-centric approach. *Smart Agric. Technol.* **9**, 100538 (2024).
18. Amenyedzi, D. K. et al. System design for a prototype acoustic network to deter avian pests in agriculture fields. *Agriculture* **15**, 10 (2025).
19. Iost Filho, F. H., Heldens, W. B., Kong, Z. & de Lange, E. S. Drones: innovative technology for use in precision pest management. *J. Econ. Entomol.* **113**, 1–25 (2020).
20. Creamer, R. E., Barel, J. M., Bongiorno, G. & Zwetsloot, M. J. The life of soils: integrating the who and how of multifunctionality. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* **166**, 108561 (2022).
21. Ozaki, R., Tsujimoto, Y., Andriamananjara, A., Rakotonindrina, H. & Sakurai, T. Optimizing fertilizer use by providing soil quality information: experimental evidence from Madagascar. *Agric. Food Secur.* **13**, 45 (2024).
22. Kik, M. C., Claassen, G. D. H., Meuwissen, M. P. M., Smit, A. B. & Saatkamp, H. W. The economic value of sustainable soil management in arable farming systems – A conceptual framework. *Eur. J. Agron.* **129**, 126334 (2021).
23. York, L. M., Griffiths, M. & Maaz, T. M. Whole-plant phenotypic engineering: moving beyond ratios for multi-objective optimization of nutrient use efficiency. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **75**, 102682 (2022).
24. Harshitha, B. S., Naveen, A., Bhargavi, H. A., Basavaraj, P. S. & Karthik Kumar, M. High-Throughput Phenotyping Enabled Rice Improvement. In *Climate-Smart Rice Breeding* (eds Singh, A., Singh, S. K. & Shrestha, J.) 249–271 (Springer, 2024). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-7098-4_10.
25. Gill, T. et al. A comprehensive review of high throughput phenotyping and machine learning for plant stress phenotyping. *Phenomics* **2**, 156–183 (2022).

26. Bazzo, C. O. G. et al. Assessing the effect of field disturbances on biomass estimation in grasslands using UAV-derived canopy height models. *PFG – J. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Geoinformation Sci.* **93**, 37–49 (2025).
27. FAO. *FAO Strategic Framework 2022-2031*. (FAO, 2021).
28. Beckmann, M. et al. Conventional land-use intensification reduces species richness and increases production: a global meta-analysis. *Glob. Change Biol.* **25**, 1941–1956 (2019).
29. Cozim-Melges, F. et al. Farming practices to enhance biodiversity across biomes: a systematic review. *npj Biodivers* **3**, 1 (2024).
30. Doxa, A. et al. Low-intensity agriculture increases farmland bird abundances in France. *J. Appl. Ecol.* **47**, 1348–1356 (2010).
31. Read, Q. D., Hondula, K. L. & Muth, M. K. Biodiversity effects of food system sustainability actions from farm to fork. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **119**, e2113884119 (2022).
32. Remelgado, R., Levers, C. & Cord, A. F. Cultivated lands: blind spots in global biodiversity data. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2025.09.017> (2025).
33. Kebede, E. A. et al. Assessing and addressing the global state of food production data scarcity. *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-024-00516-2> (2024).
34. Harbo, L. S., Olesen, J. E., Lemming, C., Christensen, B. T. & Elsgaard, L. Limitations of farm management data in analyses of decadal changes in SOC stocks in the Danish soil-monitoring network. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* **74**, e13379 (2023).
35. Burian, A. et al. Biodiversity–production feedback effects lead to intensification traps in agricultural landscapes. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-024-02349-0> (2024).
36. Scholefield, P. et al. Modelling the European farmland bird indicator in response to forecast land-use change in Europe. *Ecol. Indic.* **11**, 46–51 (2011).
37. Vihervaara, P., Basille, M., Mandon, C., Suni, T. & Lipsanen, A. *Report on the Mapping of Ministries, Agencies and Organisations That Fund and Steer National/ Sub-National Biodiversity Monitoring Schemes*. D2.3, Biodiversa+ report, <https://doi.org/10.2760/051785> (2023).
38. Johnson, T. F. et al. Revealing uncertainty in the status of biodiversity change. *Nature* **628**, 788–794 (2024).
39. Zurell, D. et al. Predicting the way forward for the Global Biodiversity Framework. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **122**, e2501695122 (2025).
40. de la Riva, E. G. et al. From functional diversity to human well-being: a conceptual framework for agroecosystem sustainability. *Agric. Syst.* **208**, 103659 (2023).
41. Lee, M.-B., Chen, D., Liu, F. & Zou, F. Effects of spatial and temporal crop changes on bird diversity in peri-urban agricultural lands. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* **80**, 138–145 (2024).
42. Ullmann, W. et al. The secret life of wild animals revealed by accelerometer data: how landscape diversity and seasonality influence the behavioural types of European hares. *Landsc. Ecol.* **38**, 3081–3095 (2023).
43. Garibaldi, L. A. et al. Working landscapes need at least 20% native habitat. *Conserv. Lett.* **14**, e12773 (2021).
44. Jeanneret, P. et al. An increase in food production in Europe could dramatically affect farmland biodiversity. *Commun. Earth Environ.* **2**, 183 (2021).
45. Gruber, T. et al. Cultural change in animals: a flexible behavioural adaptation to human disturbance. *Palgrave Commun* **5**, 64 (2019).
46. de la Torre, J. A. et al. There will be conflict – agricultural landscapes are prime, rather than marginal, habitats for Asian elephants. *Anim. Conserv.* **24**, 720–732 (2021).
47. FAO. *FAO's Plant Production and Protection Division*. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc2447en> (2022).
48. Evans, T., Angulo, E., Bradshaw, C. J. A., Turbelin, A. & Courchamp, F. Global economic costs of alien birds. *PLOS ONE* **18**, e0292854 (2023).
49. Wang, S., Deng, T., Zhang, J. & Li, Y. Global economic costs of mammal invasions. *Sci. Total Environ.* **857**, 159479 (2023).
50. Horvath, D. P., Clay, S. A., Swanton, C. J., Anderson, J. V. & Chao, W. S. Weed-induced crop yield loss: a new paradigm and new challenges. *Trends Plant Sci* **28**, 567–582 (2023).
51. Kumar, S. et al. Weed management challenges in modern agriculture: The role of environmental factors and fertilization strategies. *Crop Prot* **185**, 106903 (2024).
52. Esposito, M., Crimaldi, M., Cirillo, V., Sarghini, F. & Maggio, A. Drone and sensor technology for sustainable weed management: a review. *Chem. Biol. Technol. Agric.* **8**, 18 (2021).
53. Widén, A. et al. Playbacks of predator vocalizations reduce crop damage by ungulates. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* **328**, 107853 (2022).
54. Park, Y.-L., Naharki, K., Karimzadeh, R., Seo, B. Y. & Lee, G.-S. Rapid assessment of insect pest outbreak using drones: a case study with *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in soybean fields. *Insects* **14**, 555 (2023).
55. Keshet, D., Brook, A., Malkinson, D., Izhaki, I. & Charter, M. The use of drones to determine rodent location and damage in agricultural crops. *Drones* **6**, 396 (2022).
56. Friesenhahn, B. A. et al. Using drones to detect and quantify wild pig damage and yield loss in corn fields throughout plant growth stages. *Wildl. Soc. Bull.* **47**, e1437 (2023).
57. Seidl, M., González, E., Kadlec, T., Saska, P. & Knapp, M. Temporary non-crop habitats within arable fields: The effects of field defects on carabid beetle assemblages. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* **293**, 106856 (2020).
58. Chesmore, D. & Nellenbach, C. Acoustic methods for the automated detection and identification of insects. *Acta Hortic* **562**, 223–231 (2001).
59. Sandoval-Pillajo, L., García-Santillán, I., Pusedá-Chulde, M. & Giret, A. Weed detection based on deep learning from UAV imagery: a review. *Smart Agric. Technol.* **12**, 101147 (2025).
60. Fischer, S., Edwards, A. C., Garnett, S. T., Whiteside, T. G. & Weber, P. Drones and sound recorders increase the number of bird species identified: a combined surveys approach. *Ecol. Inform.* **74**, 101988 (2023).
61. Rahman, D. A. et al. Developing a new method using thermal drones for population surveys of the world's rarest great ape species, *Pongo tapanuliensis*. *Glob. Ecol. Conserv.* **58**, e03463 (2025).
62. Delisle, Z. J., Flaherty, E. A., Nobbe, M. R., Wzientek, C. M. & Swihart, R. K. Next-generation camera trapping: systematic review of historic trends suggests keys to expanded research applications in ecology and conservation. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **9**, 617996 (2021).
63. Roilo, S., Hofmeester, T. R., Frauendorf, M., Widén, A. & Cord, A. F. The untapped potential of camera traps for farmland biodiversity monitoring: current practice and outstanding agroecological questions. *Remote Sens. Ecol. Conserv.* **11**, 243–254 (2024).
64. van Klink, R. et al. Emerging technologies revolutionise insect ecology and monitoring. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* **37**, 872–885 (2022).
65. Hoefler, S., McKnight, D. T., Allen-Ankins, S., Nordberg, E. J. & Schwarzkopf, L. Passive acoustic monitoring in terrestrial vertebrates: a review. *Bioacoustics* **32**, 506–531 (2023).
66. Axford, D., Sohel, F., Vanderklift, M. A. & Hodgson, A. J. Collectively advancing deep learning for animal detection in drone imagery: Successes, challenges, and research gaps. *Ecol. Inform.* **83**, 102842 (2024).
67. James, K. & Bradshaw, K. Detecting plant species in the field with deep learning and drone technology. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **11**, 1509–1519 (2020).
68. Kahl, S., Wood, C. M., Eibl, M. & Klinck, H. BirdNET: a deep learning solution for avian diversity monitoring. *Ecol. Inform.* **61**, 101236 (2021).
69. Tabak, M. A. et al. Machine learning to classify animal species in camera trap images: applications in ecology. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **10**, 585–590 (2019).

70. UN. *The Global Threat of Drying Lands*. (United Nations, 2024).
71. Tarolli, P., Luo, J., Park, E., Barcaccia, G. & Masin, R. Soil salinization in agriculture: mitigation and adaptation strategies combining nature-based solutions and bioengineering. *iScience* **27**, 108830 (2024).
72. FAO. *Global Status of Salt-Affected Soils*. (FAO, 2024).
73. Silvero, N. E. Q. et al. Chapter Three - Sensing technologies for characterizing and monitoring soil functions: a review. in *Advances in Agronomy* (ed. Sparks, D. L.) vol. 177 125–168 (Academic Press, 2023).
74. Padilla, F. M., Fameselli, M., Gianquinto, G., Tei, F. & Thompson, R. B. Monitoring nitrogen status of vegetable crops and soils for optimal nitrogen management. *Agric. Water Manag.* **241**, 106356 (2020).
75. Rinot, O., Levy, G. J., Steinberger, Y., Svoray, T. & Eshel, G. Soil health assessment: a critical review of current methodologies and a proposed new approach. *Sci. Total Environ.* **648**, 1484–1491 (2019).
76. Bünemann, E. K. et al. Soil quality – A critical review. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* **120**, 105–125 (2018).
77. Diaz-Gonzalez, F. A., Vuelvas, J., Correa, C. A., Vallejo, V. E. & Patino, D. Machine learning and remote sensing techniques applied to estimate soil indicators. *Review. Ecol. Indic.* **135**, 108517 (2022).
78. Acosta-Dacal, A. et al. Optimization and validation of a QuEChERS-based method for the simultaneous environmental monitoring of 218 pesticide residues in clay loam soil. *Sci. Total Environ.* **753**, 142015 (2021).
79. Fenz, S., Neubauer, T., Friedel, J. K. & Wohlmuth, M.-L. AI- and data-driven crop rotation planning. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **212**, 108160 (2023).
80. Ruppert, K. M., Kline, R. J. & Rahman, M. S. Past, present, and future perspectives of environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding: A systematic review in methods, monitoring, and applications of global eDNA. *Glob. Ecol. Conserv.* **17**, e00547 (2019).
81. Skidmore, A. K. et al. eDNA biodiversity from space: predicting soil bacteria and fungi alpha diversity in forests using DESIS satellite remote sensing. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 1–31 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2025.2464958> (2025).
82. FAO. *The Impact of Disasters on Agriculture and Food Security 2023 – Avoiding and Reducing Losses through Investment in Resilience*. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc7900en> (FAO, 2023).
83. Kotz, M., Kuik, F., Lis, E. & Nickel, C. Global warming and heat extremes to enhance inflationary pressures. *Commun. Earth Environ.* **5**, 116 (2024).
84. Mansoor, S. & Chung, Y. S. Functional phenotyping: understanding the dynamic response of plants to drought stress. *Curr. Plant Biol.* **38**, 100331 (2024).
85. Wang, S. et al. Airborne hyperspectral imaging of cover crops through radiative transfer process-guided machine learning. *Remote Sens. Environ.* **285**, 113386 (2023).
86. Rivera, G., Porras, R., Florencia, R. & Sánchez-Solís, J. P. LiDAR applications in precision agriculture for cultivating crops: A review of recent advances. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **207**, 107737 (2023).
87. Aquilani, C., Confessore, A., Bozzi, R., Sirtori, F. & Pugliese, C. Review: precision livestock farming technologies in pasture-based livestock systems. *Animal* **16**, 100429 (2022).
88. Librán-Embid, F., Klaus, F., Tscharrntke, T. & Grass, I. Unmanned aerial vehicles for biodiversity-friendly agricultural landscapes - a systematic review. *Sci. Total Environ.* **732**, 139204 (2020).
89. Stone, T. C. & Davis, K. J. Using unmanned aerial vehicles to estimate body volume at scale for ecological monitoring. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **16**, 317–331 (2025).
90. FAO. *World Food and Agriculture – Statistical Yearbook* (FAO, 2024).
91. Deyle, E. R., May, R. M., Munch, S. B. & Sugihara, G. Tracking and forecasting ecosystem interactions in real time. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* **283**, 20152258 (2016).
92. Braczkowski, A. R. et al. The unequal burden of human-wildlife conflict. *Commun. Biol.* **6**, 182 (2023).
93. Püttmanns, M. et al. No seasonal curtailment of the Eurasian Skylark's (*Auda arvensis*) breeding season in German heterogeneous farmland. *Ecol. Evol.* **12**, e9267 (2022).
94. Boyd, R. J., Powney, G. D. & Pescott, O. L. We need to talk about nonprobability samples. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* **38**, 521–531 (2023).
95. Gonzalez, A. et al. A global biodiversity observing system to unite monitoring and guide action. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02171-0> (2023).
96. Kernecker, M. et al. Transition zones across agricultural field boundaries for integrated landscape research and management of biodiversity and yields. *Ecol. Solut. Evid.* **3**, e12122 (2022).
97. Jones, S. K. et al. Achieving win-win outcomes for biodiversity and yield through diversified farming. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* **67**, 14–31 (2023).
98. Pereira, H. M. et al. Essential biodiversity variables. *Science* **339**, 277–278 (2013).
99. Skidmore, A. K. et al. Priority list of biodiversity metrics to observe from space. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* **5**, 896–906 (2021).
100. Jetz, W. et al. Essential biodiversity variables for mapping and monitoring species populations. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* **3**, 539–551 (2019).
101. OECD. *The Post-2020 Biodiversity Framework: Targets, Indicators and Measurability Implications at Global and National Level*. (OECD, 2019).
102. Lumbierres, M. et al. Towards implementing workflows for essential biodiversity variables at a European scale. *Glob. Ecol. Conserv.* **62**, e03699 (2025).
103. Maguiña, R., Casabella-Herrero, G., Bota, G. & Brotons, L. Developing and deploying new technologies for biodiversity monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880523> (2024).
104. Buchmann, C. M. & Schurr, F. M. A ready-to use workflow for automated, sound-based bird identification and localization. *bioRxiv* <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.07.02.601711> (2024).
105. Kühl, H. S. et al. Effective biodiversity monitoring needs a culture of integration. *One Earth* **3**, 462–474 (2020).
106. Geizendorffer, I. R. et al. EDITOR'S choice: how much would it cost to monitor farmland biodiversity in Europe? *J. Appl. Ecol.* **53**, 140–149 (2016).
107. Juffe-Bignoli, D. et al. Assessing the cost of global biodiversity and conservation knowledge. *PLoS ONE* **11**, 1–22 (2016).
108. United Nations University. *World Income Inequality Database. WIID*, (UN, 2022).
109. FAO. AgriTech Observatory. <https://agritechobservatory.fao.org/> (FAO, 2024).
110. Prasad, P. V. V. et al. Patterns of investment in agricultural research and innovation for the Global South, with a focus on sustainable agricultural intensification. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **7**, 1108949 (2023).
111. Schulz, D. & Börner, J. Innovation context and technology traits explain heterogeneity across studies of agricultural technology adoption: A meta-analysis. *J. Agric. Econ.* **74**, 570–590 (2023).
112. Dibbern, T., Romani, L. A. S. & Massruhá, S. M. F. S. Main drivers and barriers to the adoption of Digital Agriculture technologies. *Smart Agric. Technol.* **8**, 100459 (2024).
113. Kendall, H. et al. Precision agriculture technology adoption: a qualitative study of small-scale commercial “family farms” located in the North China Plain. *Precis. Agric.* **23**, 319–351 (2022).
114. Mizik, T. How can precision farming work on a small scale? A systematic literature review. *Precis. Agric.* **24**, 384–406 (2023).
115. Olvermann, M., Hornung, J. & Kauffeld, S. ‘We Could Be Much Further Ahead’ -Multidimensional Drivers and Barriers for Agricultural Transition. *J. Rural Stud.* **97**, 153–166 (2023).
116. Nxumalo, G. S. & Chauke, H. Challenges and opportunities in smallholder agriculture digitization in South Africa. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **9**, 1583224 (2025).

117. Miine, L. K., Akorsu, A. D., Boampong, O. & Bukari, S. Digital agriculture and decent working conditions of smallholder farmers and farmworkers in Ghana. *Discov. Food* **4**, 173 (2024).
118. Lowder, S. K., Sánchez, M. V. & Bertini, R. Which farms feed the world and has farmland become more concentrated?. *World Dev* **142**, 105455 (2021).
119. Caldwell, I. R. et al. Global trends and biases in biodiversity conservation research. *Cell Rep. Sustain.* **1**, 100082 (2024).
120. EC. *Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027: Strategic Plans at a Glance*. (EC, 2023).
121. FAO & ITU. *Status of Digital Agriculture in 18 Countries of Europe and Central Asia*. (FAO, 2020).
122. FAO & ITU. *Status of Digital Agriculture in 47 Sub-Saharan African Countries*. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb7943en> (FAO, 2022).
123. Zezza, A., Gourlay, S. & Molini, V. Closing the data gap in agriculture through sustainable investment in the data value chain: Realizing the vision of the 50x2030 Initiative. *Stat. J. IAOS* **38**, 1–6 (2022).
124. FAO. *The Agri-NBSAPs Support Initiative: Supporting Countries in Their National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans for the Agrifood Sectors*. (GFAO, 2024).
125. Schroeder, K., Lampietti, J. & Elabed, G. *What's Cooking: Digital Transformation of the Agrifood System*. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-1657-4> (2021).
126. Vijayakumar, S. et al. Precision weed control using unmanned aerial vehicles and robots: assessing feasibility, bottlenecks, and recommendations for scaling. *NDT* **3**, 10 (2025).
127. Abdulai, A.-R. Toward digitalization futures in smallholder farming systems in Sub-Sahara Africa: a social practice proposal. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **6**, 866331 (2022).
128. Lyu, Z., Jing, Z. & Yang, X. Bridging the digital divide for sustainable agriculture: how digital adoption strengthens farmer livelihood resilience. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **9**, 1628588 (2025).
129. McCarthy, C. et al. Can drones help smallholder farmers improve agriculture efficiencies and reduce food insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa? Local perceptions from Malawi. *Agriculture* **13**, 13051075 (2023).
130. Christiansen, G., Simonneaux, J. & Hazard, L. The human being at the heart of agroecological transitions: insights from cognitive mapping of actors' vision of change in Roquefort area. *Agric. Hum. Values* **40**, 1675–1696 (2023).
131. Pe'er, G. et al. How can the European Common Agricultural Policy help halt biodiversity loss? Recommendations by over 300 experts. *Conserv. Lett.* **15**, e12901 (2022).
132. Hölting, L. et al. Co-design: working with farmers in Europe to halt the loss of biological diversity. *Ecol. Solut. Evid.* **3**, e12169 (2022).
133. Mennig, P. A never-ending story of reforms: on the wicked nature of the common agricultural policy. *npj Sustain. Agric.* **2**, 20 (2024).
134. Hecker, L. P., Sturm, A., Querhammer, L. & Wätzold, F. Cost-effectiveness of state-dependent versus state-independent agri-environment schemes for biodiversity conservation. *Ecol. Econ.* **217**, 108088 (2024).
135. Chamorro-Padial, J., Garcia, R. & Gil, R. A systematic review of open data in agriculture. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **219**, 108775 (2024).
136. Basel, A. M., Nguyen, K. T., Arnaud, E. & Craparo, A. C. W. The foundations of big data sharing: a CGIAR international research organization perspective. *Front. Environ. Sci.* **11**, 131635 (2023).
137. Ewert, F. et al. FAIRagro - A FAIR Data Infrastructure for Agrosystems (proposal). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366884> (2023).
138. Burchfield, E. et al. Towards a comprehensive analysis of agricultural land systems in the EU and US: a critical view on publicly available datasets. *Land Use Policy* **147**, 107371 (2024).
139. Schneider, M., Schelte, T., Schmitz, F. & Körner, M. EuroCrops: the largest harmonized open crop dataset across the European Union. *Sci. Data* **10**, 612 (2023).
140. Stone, G. D. Surveillance agriculture and peasant autonomy. *J. Agrar. Change* **22**, 608–631 (2022).
141. Lampach, N. et al. Statistical atlas of European agriculture: gridded data from the agricultural census 2020 and the spatial distribution of CAP contextual indicators. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **17**, 3893–3919 (2025).
142. *Data Act – The Path to the Digital Decade*. (Publications Office of the European Union, 2022). <https://doi.org/10.2775/98413>.
143. Kimble, M. et al. medna-metadata: an open-source data management system for tracking environmental DNA samples and metadata. *Bioinformatics* **38**, 4589–4597 (2022).
144. Anthony, M. A., Bender, S. F. & Heijden, M. G. A. van der. Enumerating soil biodiversity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **120**, e2304663120 (2023).
145. Steen, K. A., Therkildsen, O. R., Green, O. & Karstoft, H. Detection of bird nests during mechanical weeding by incremental background modeling and visual saliency. *Sensors* **15**, 5096–5111 (2015).
146. Silva del Pozo, M., Body, G., Rerig, G. & Basille, M. *Guide on Harmonising Biodiversity Monitoring Protocols across Scales*. vol. Biodiversa+ report (EU, 2023).
147. UNEP-WCMC. Headline Indicator on biodiversity information for monitoring the global biodiversity framework. *Indicators for the Kunming – Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* <https://www.gbif-indicators.org/metadata/headline/21-1> (UNEP, 2025).

Acknowledgements

This work was made possible by the European Union (Horizon Europe project EarthBridge, grant agreement no. 101079310). EP was also funded by the European Union (ERC, BEAST, 101044740). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. RR and AFC were also supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy (EXC 2070; Grant No. 390732324) and the German Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTR) within the Research Initiative for the Conservation of Biodiversity (FEEdA) for the ECO²SCAPE project (Funding code: 03LW0079K). Finally, we would like to give special thanks to Thomas Döring from the University of Bonn for his support in reviewing this manuscript prior to submission.

Author contributions

R.R. and A.F.C. designed the study. R.R. led the conceptualization and writing in collaboration with A.F.C., with additional contributions from M.B., M.V., E.P., M.P., P.V., C.M., A.E., and D.R. R.R. designed the figures.

Funding

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

Supplementary information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44264-025-00118-5>.

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